

Event metadata

Event title	Building the future of bioinformatics with Nextflow: Technical innovation, community engagement, and career development opportunities
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	19 September 2024
Time of event	12 pm AEST
Topic description	Discover how Nextflow is transforming the bioinformatics landscape with cutting-edge pipelining solutions. This webinar will explore the technical advantages of Nextflow, highlight ways to engage with a thriving global community, and provide valuable insights into career growth opportunities within this ecosystem. Whether you're new to the field or an experienced bioinformatician, this webinar will equip you with the knowledge and tools to catch the wave of new developments, drive innovation in your projects and connect with the wider research community.
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/nextflow-gvda
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Workflow Pipeline
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	Life scientists and bioinformaticians who need to use and recreate reproducible data analysis workflows.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None

Learning outcomes	Gain knowledge and tools to drive innovation in bioinformatics projects and connect with the wider research community.
Speakers	Dr Geraldine Van der Auwera, Lead Developer Advocate at Seqera
Related material	None